

Influence of Engagement and Job Satisfaction on the Flow State of volunteers in a non-governmental Organisation in the Republic of Perú

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Abstract

Background: Non-governmental organisations (NGOs) rely heavily on volunteer work to achieve their social objectives, fostering inclusive and sustainable environments. Key factors such as commitment, autonomy, recognition, and job satisfaction are essential to enhance volunteer performance. The opportunities provided by NGOs help volunteers thrive in a positive environment that promotes satisfaction and enriching experiences.

Objective: This study aimed to analyse the influence of engagement (ENG) and work satisfaction (WS) on the flow state of volunteers in non-governmental organisations (NGOs) in Peru.

Methodology: The research is quantitative, non-experimental, hypothetical-deductive, and uses a cross-sectional design. The sample consisted of 1,023 volunteers from the NGO under study. Three standardised instruments were used for data collection: UWES-9 for ENG, S20/23 for WS, and WOLF for Flow.

Results: The results showed that ENG and WS explained 70.8% of the variability in Flow, with a strong positive correlation between ENG and WS (0.769). ENG significantly impacted Flow (coefficient 0.65), as did WS (coefficient 0.45). Higher levels of ENG and WS among volunteers reinforce Flow. Emphasis is placed on an inclusive and sustainable work environment to enhance volunteer engagement and effectiveness. However, there is a clear need for training, recognition, and emotional support for the staff.

Conclusions: Engaged volunteers who feel recognised and supported experience greater job satisfaction, which enhances Flow—a state of immersion and enjoyment in activities. This relationship underscores the importance of creating work environments with challenges, good conditions, and development opportunities that support volunteer engagement. Self-determination and role theories highlight autonomy, competence, and relationships as crucial elements.

Contribution: This research extends the Demands-Resources Model and Self-Determination Theory (SDT) by examining the role of engagement, satisfaction, and flow in volunteering. It provides guidance to NGOs on improving volunteer management through training, recognition, and supportive practices, thereby enhancing retention, satisfaction, and overall organisational impact.

Recommendations: To boost satisfaction and retention, NGOs should provide training and recognition, align tasks with skills, improve working conditions, and ensure volunteer participation and development opportunities.

Keywords: engagement; job satisfaction; flow state; volunteering; non-governmental organisations.

Introduction

People play a fundamental role in organisations (Rozo-Sánchez et al., 2019). Regardless of an organization's nature, people steer its course, whether through leadership at the managerial level or by carrying out essential operational processes. They respond to a mission that sets their direction and guides sustainable actions within a social scope that complements important economic aspects (Alonso-Almeida et al., 2015).

Sustainability is built from global agreements and pacts promoted by international organisations such as the OECD, UNESCO, and the Inter-American Development Bank, who, aligned with the 2030 Agenda and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), undertake efforts to direct collective actions, develop inclusive programs, and move towards a more sustainable future that generates contributions and social well-being, in harmony with stakeholders and the environment.

Some organisations are founded with the mission of providing support pathways and developing social community service work aimed at vulnerable populations in situations and realities that require attention. They do not pursue profit motives or pay taxes to governments; they are non-governmental organisations (NGOs) supported by volunteer groups that work cooperatively and collaboratively.

In this case, the experiences of an NGO supporting the education of children, from basic to higher levels, are presented. With a comprehensive vision, it addresses training processes with a focus on entrepreneurship and provides healthcare services for both the children and their families. In these types of organisations, volunteers take on the role of mentors, represented by young women with university education and high levels of commitment to social causes. Due to the voluntary nature of their work, they do not receive a competitive salary compared to the private sector. However, their intrinsic motivation and desire to contribute positively to the community are essential for achieving the NGO's goals.

Given the importance of volunteers, NGOs must maintain their commitment and effectiveness, well-being, life satisfaction, and emotional balance, as outlined in the World Happiness Report (Helliwell et al., 2023). In Latin American countries, despite the interest in this type of work, the management for the development of essential processes is often deemed inefficient and obstructed by lengthy procedures required by those acting as volunteers. This leads to low satisfaction, high turnover (Cepal, 2023), and burnout. In Spain, 60% of organisations face difficulties in retaining volunteers long-term; social work is undervalued, and given economic restrictions, volunteers are not adequately trained, leading to challenges in executing support and social integration processes (United Nations Volunteers, 2021).

In this context, it becomes crucial to provide emotional and professional support to volunteers (World Bank, 2023), define mechanisms to retain them and keep them committed to their social role. Inclusive social practices are essential for reducing inequalities and protecting people's rights. This research aims to analyse the influence of engagement (ENG) and job satisfaction (WS) on the flow state of volunteers in a non-governmental organisation (NGO).

The flow state refers to a mental state in which a person is fully immersed in an activity, experiencing a deep sense of concentration, enjoyment, and a loss of the sense of time. For volunteers, achieving this state involves being in an environment that fosters the alignment between their skills and the tasks they perform. In the context of an NGO, this is relevant for strengthening the bond between the volunteer and the organisation, as it allows volunteers to experience a sense of accomplishment and deep connection with their activities, thereby contributing to sustained organisational impact and higher volunteer retention. Furthermore, flow promotes continuous and motivated participation in community work, helping to maintain long-term commitment to the NGO's mission. This analysis is essential for understanding and improving the conditions that enhance engagement and job satisfaction, promoting a flow state that enriches the volunteer experience and effectiveness.

This study is essential for understanding how volunteer engagement and job satisfaction in NGOs affect their performance and experience. Identifying the conditions that motivate them allows for the development of management strategies that foster inclusive work environments, thus improving volunteer retention and enhancing NGOs' social impact. Furthermore, this approach aligns with Sustainable Development Goal 8, which promotes decent work and economic growth, contributing to the well-being of communities and long-term sustainable development.

Literature Review: Engagement, Job Satisfaction, and Flow

In organisations, workers represent valuable talent working toward achieving business objectives. They embody invaluable intellectual human capital that, through their performance, significantly contributes to the development of management processes, even from the operational level of activities. Their commitment is essential, mainly if their work is carried out voluntarily by participating in social, community, or public organisations aiming to support vulnerable groups in society.

Organisations, and particularly NGOs, must rely on highly committed teams to achieve their objectives. Their goals are social, and those participating often do so voluntarily. The staff of these organisations must demonstrate initiatives to satisfy their motivations (Clary & Snyder, 1999), feel valuable, committed, dedicated, enthusiastic, energetic, delighted, and maintain a positive attitude (Schaufeli et al., 2013). They choose to be part of this context, seeking to create bonds of satisfaction with what they do; they assume obligations and responsibilities diligently and demonstrate motivating states that reflect effort, determination, and attention.

Work with engagement generates satisfaction, which is associated with a positive and pleasurable emotional state based on the subjective perception of the individual's work experiences (Pizarro et al., 2019). This person expresses levels of job happiness, health, and well-being, with a positive attitude toward work.

The objective of the research is to analyse the influence of engagement (ENG) and job satisfaction (WS) on the flow state of volunteers in a non-governmental organisation (NGO). To achieve this, the study sought to determine the relationship between volunteer engagement and job satisfaction to understand how these factors are interrelated and contribute to job well-being in this context. It also aims to evaluate the impact of engagement on the flow state experienced by volunteers, exploring whether a higher level of commitment is associated with greater immersion and enjoyment in their volunteer activities. Similarly, the study aimed to analyse the influence of job satisfaction on the flow state of volunteers, considering whether greater satisfaction in their work environment fosters a higher level of flow.

Commitment to what one does denotes engagement (ENG), which is enhanced when the environment satisfies the basic needs of those who collaborate (Schaufeli, 2013; Gürbüz et al., 2023; Mazzetti et al., 2023; Rahmadani et al., 2023). ENG acts as a mediator in the relationship between working conditions and job satisfaction. Better working conditions foster ENG, which in turn increases job satisfaction. This mediational model suggests that efforts to improve the work environment have a dual impact, increasing both ENG and individual' satisfaction (Agmapisarn & Khetjenkarn, 2024).

Both constructs, ENG and WS, share characteristics conducive to experiencing flow. ENG facilitates task absorption and concentration, while WS provides a positive emotional

foundation and well-being that supports these intense immersion experiences. This dual effect creates an optimal environment for entering flow.

The work carried out by volunteer groups requires support for less advantaged vulnerable groups. Driven by spontaneity and commitment, the work performed generates levels of satisfaction and happiness, motivating people to work towards fulfilling activities and assuming responsibilities (Schaufeli, 2013), with which they will be satisfied (not due to external and economic resources they may receive, but because of the enjoyment of performing the activity) (García-Pérez, 2013; Pradhan et al., 2017). Based on this, the research proposes the hypothesis:

H1: *Engagement is related to job satisfaction.*

In this context, experiences are described where individuals become fully engaged in an activity, dedicating themselves, concentrating, and committing, experiencing high levels of performance and enjoyment (Pizarro et al., 2019; Cueto et al., 2024; Ruz et al., 2019), creating an emotionally positive environment, where motivation and satisfaction with task development are evident.

In this state of total immersion in tasks, the individual is completely absorbed and focused, also called absorption (Bakker, 2008; Liu et al., 2021). A flow state is evident in the person, allowing them to face work demands and maximise their resources (Bakker & de Vries, 2021). This dual state of high energy and emotional well-being facilitates entry into flow, allowing employees to focus and fully enjoy their work activities.

ENG and the flow state share similar characteristics, such as energy, focus, and absorption in work activities. ENG facilitates entry into the flow state (Pizarro et al., 2019; Huang, 2024; Li & Gong, 2024) and acts as a precursor to it, with a direct and significant relationship between motivation, job satisfaction, and flow state in workers (Pizarro et al., 2019). Based on this demonstrated relationship, the hypothesis is formulated:

H2: *Engagement has an impact on the flow state.*

Completing meaningful tasks, recognition for work well done, positive relationships with colleagues and supervisors, and the perception of fairness in the work environment generate satisfaction in individuals and positive, favourable work states. These positive experiences manifest happiness, motivation, health, and well-being, representing a positive and pleasurable emotional state that contributes to the achievement of goals and objectives (Cueto, et al., 2024).

Satisfaction levels depend on intrinsic and extrinsic factors (Park & Johnson, 2019). The former is related to aspects inherent to human beings that lead to full satisfaction, referring to experiences of pleasure and fulfilment (Csikszentmihalyi, 1990), while the latter stems from extrinsic conditions in which the activity takes place and contributes to satisfaction. A collaborator who is satisfied with workplace conditions has provided resources and a good work climate and has received benefits that positively contribute to engagement.

Satisfying basic psychological needs for autonomy, competence, and interpersonal relationships improves job satisfaction (WS). When these needs are met, employees experience greater well-being and satisfaction, facilitating entry into the flow state (Deterding & Cutting, 2023), leading to a high ENG level. Employees feel more competent and autonomous in their tasks, essential to experiencing flow. Therefore, it is proposed:

H3: *Job satisfaction affects the flow state. The work resources that contribute to job satisfaction (WS) also promote flow.*

Engagement or commitment and job satisfaction are two concepts that can help explain the flow state at work. Social support, positive feedback, and autonomy in the workplace increase job satisfaction and facilitate entry into flow by providing the necessary conditions for high concentration and enjoyment at work (Bakker, 2008a; Bellini et al., 2022). Therefore, the hypothesis is proposed:

H4: *Engagement and job satisfaction together influence the flow state.*

Based on this, the following research model is proposed. (Figure 1):

Figure 1: Research model

Methods

The research was conducted using a quantitative approach, and a hypothetical-deductive method was adopted, which involved the formulation of hypotheses supported by theoretical references that allow for their validation. The hypothesis testing is based on the collection and analysis of empirical data. The design was cross-sectional and non-experimental, with the study sample consisting of 1,023 volunteers from an NGO, selected through a non-probabilistic convenience sampling method, meeting the requirements for a representative sample using a multivariable technique, where it was necessary to have more than 200 observations for both factor analysis and to validate the proposed model.

For data collection, three standardised instruments were used: a) The Work Engagement Scale (UWES-9); b) The Job Satisfaction Questionnaire (S20/23) (Meliá & Peiró, 1998); c)

The Work-Related Flow Inventory (WOLF), which measures the degree of immersion and enjoyment in work (Bakker, 2008b). Cronbach's Alpha values were calculated to assess the internal consistency of the instruments. Additionally, Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) (Chión y Charles, 2016). sample adequacy tests and Bartlett's test of sphericity were conducted to confirm the suitability of the data for factor analysis.

Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) was also performed to identify the underlying structure of Flow, followed by Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) to validate the defined structure, meeting one of the criteria for validating a questionnaire through a statistical approach. A Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) approach was used to examine the hypothesised relationships. Finally, regression analysis was conducted to evaluate the model's explanatory power and confirm the results' significance.

The research was structured under a non-experimental and cross-sectional design, adopting a quantitative and hypothetical-deductive approach. This method included the formulation of hypotheses supported by theoretical frameworks, which were later verified through the collection and analysis of empirical data. The study population consisted of volunteers from a non-governmental organisation (NGO) in Peru. The sample size was 1,023 volunteers, a sufficient number to meet the representativeness requirements of the multivariable analysis technique, especially for factor analysis and the validation of the proposed model. Participant selection was carried out through non-probabilistic convenience sampling based on the availability of the volunteers and aimed at achieving adequate representativeness for the planned statistical analyses.

To measure the study variables, three standardised data collection instruments were used: the Work Engagement Scale (UWES-9), used to assess volunteer commitment; the Job Satisfaction Questionnaire (S20/23) by Meliá and Peiró (1998), which measures job satisfaction; and the Work-Related Flow Inventory (WOLF) by Bakker (2008), which evaluates the degree of immersion and enjoyment in work tasks.

The reliability of the instruments was verified by calculating Cronbach's Alpha coefficient for each scale, which confirmed their internal consistency and appropriateness for this research context. Additionally, sample adequacy tests, including Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's test of sphericity, were applied, confirming the data's suitability for factor analysis. Subsequently, exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was performed to identify the underlying structure of each construct, followed by confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) to validate the theoretical structure of the employed instruments.

Regarding the data collection method, the questionnaires were administered to the NGO volunteers through standardised procedures, ensuring the confidentiality of participants. Finally, the data analysis method included applying a structural equation model (SEM) to assess the hypothesised relationships between ENG, WS, and FLOW. This analysis allowed for identifying the magnitude and significance of each proposed relationship. In addition, a regression analysis was conducted to evaluate the model's explanatory power and confirm the results' significance.

Results

Table 1. Characterisation of the Sample - Descriptive Data

Category	Frequency	Sample	%	Total
Gender	Male	376	36.8	1023
	Female	647	63.2	
Age	18-25	144	14.1	1023
	26-30	437	42.7	
	31-35	168	16.4	
	36-40	97	9.5	
	41-45	93	9.1	
	46-50	24	2.3	
	51-55	60	5.9	
Level of study	Complete Secondary	60	5.9	1023
	Technical professional	126	12.3	
	University graduate	683	66.8	
	University student	153	15	
Years of experience	0	51	5	1023
	1	90	8.8	
	2	105	10.3	
	3	228	22.3	
	4	195	19.1	
	5	205	20	
	6	148	14.5	

Contrast between gender and level of study

			Complete Secondary	Technical professional	University graduate	University student
Gender	Male	%	2.3%	0.0%	25.0%	9.5%
	Female	%	3.6%	12.3%	41.8%	5.5%
Total		%	5.9%	12.3%	66.8%	15.0%

Contrast between years of experience and gender

			0	1	2	3	4
Gender	Male	%	7.0%	7.8%	5.4%	10.0%	5.0%
	Female	%	9.0%	10.2%	10.6%	13.0%	22.0%
Total		%	16.0%	18.0%	16.0%	23.0%	27.0%

Table 1 shows data from the empirical work conducted in the research on the volunteer sample. The sample predominantly comprises women (63.2%) aged 26-30 years (42.7%). Regarding educational background, most have completed university education (66.8%), followed by those with technical education (12.3%). It is also noted that 15% are currently pursuing university studies. Of the sample analysed, 22.3% have 3 years of experience, followed by those with 5 years (20%) and 4 years (19.1%). NGOs attract and retain volunteers with attractive educational profiles and experience, essential for developing management and retention strategies.

Table 2. Cronbach's Alpha Test and KMO and Bartlett

Latent variables	Cronbach's Alpha Test and	Elements
Engagement	,945	17
Job satisfaction	,948	23
KMO and Bartlett test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		,783
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Aprox. X ²	19481,357
	GI	78
	Sig.	,000

In Table 2, In Table 2, the Cronbach's Alpha values are above 0.7, indicating that the scales used are consistent. The items are correlated, and the constructs of ENG and WS are consistently measured. Additionally, the KMO measure of 0.783 indicates an adequate sampling quality, making the data suitable for factor analysis. Bartlett's Test of Sphericity is significant ($p < 0.001$), confirming that the items of the variables are related and that factor analysis is appropriate.

Table 3: Matrix of obtained factors

Factor	Description	% of variance	Puntuaction
F1: Absorption	Reflects immersion and enjoyment in work	58,954	0.914
F2: Intrinsic Motivation	Relationship with happiness	9,852	0.792
F3: Engagement	Positive feeling at work	9,198	0.504

Table 3 shows that absorption (F1) is the most influential component in the flow state, followed by intrinsic motivation (F2) and, finally, immersion (F3). Together, these factors capture different aspects of the volunteers' work experience, collectively explaining a significant proportion of the variability in their work experiences.

Table 4: CFA

Models	RMSE							X ² normado
	X ²	A	CFI	TLI	NFI	PCFI	PNFI	

			0.91	0.91	0.91	0.49			
Model 1	0	0.061	8	9	6	1	0.490	985.215	3.517
Modified model	0	0.048	5	1	3	7	0.576	789.765	1.218
Fit criteria	< 0.05		>0.9	>0.9	>0.9			Less is better	<3.0

Table 4 and figure 2 shows that the modified model provides a better fit, with an RMSEA of 0.048. Additionally, the values for CFI (0.945), TLI (0.931), and NFI (0.963) in the modified model are all above 0.9. The AIC (789.765) indicates that the modified model is more parsimonious and better fits the data. The normed χ^2 value (1.218) meets the criterion $\chi^2/df < 3$ for model validation (Hair et al., 2004), further supporting a better fit compared to the initial model.

Figure 2: Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Table 5: Level of relationship between independent variables and SEM model relationship

		WS	ENG
WS	Pearson correlation	1	,769**
	Sig. (unilateral)		,000
	N	1203	1203
ENG	Pearson correlation	,769**	1
	Sig. (unilateral)	,000	

N	1203	1203
Relationship	Coefficient	Significance
ENG--> Flow	0.650	p < 0.001
WS --> Flow	0.450	p < 0.001

The table 5 presents the correlations between the independent variables (0.769), indicating a strong positive relationship. As job satisfaction increases, engagement also increases, and vice versa. Additionally, the coefficient of 0.65 indicates that engagement has an influence on the state of flow, representing 65%. The coefficient of 0.45 indicates a moderate influence of job satisfaction on the state of flow, representing 45%. Both results are statistically significant ($p < 0.001$), reinforcing the model's validity.

Table 6: Linear regression

Resume of the model ^b									
Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Estándar error	Change in R ²	Change in F	gl	gl2	Sig. en F
1	,842 ^a	,708	,708	,384	,708	1455,847	2	1200	,000

a. Predictors: (Constant), ENG, WS
b. Dependet variable: Flow

In Table 6, the R value is 0.842, indicating a strong correlation between the variables. The R² is 0.708, meaning that approximately 70.8% of the variability in Flow can be explained by WS and ENG. The F statistic for the change in R² is 1455.847, with a significance level of $p < 0.001$, suggesting that the model is significant.

Figure 3: Relationship between the adjusted predicted value and the Flow state.

Figure 3 shows the regression line with a positive slope, indicating that as the predicted values of ENG and WS increase, Flow also increases.

Figure 4. SEM Design

Figure 4 illustrates the relationships between ENG, WS, and Flow, confirming the validity of the proposed hypotheses. The results show a strong relationship between ENG and WS,

with a high Pearson correlation of 0.769, supporting hypothesis H1. ENG significantly impacts Flow, as indicated by a coefficient of 0.65 in the SEM, thereby confirming hypothesis H2. WS also affects Flow, with a coefficient of 0.45, supporting hypothesis H3.

The model demonstrates that ENG and WS together influence the flow state, backed by an adjusted R^2 of 0.708. This explains that 70.8% of the variability in Flow is accounted for by these two variables, thus confirming hypothesis H4.

Discussion

The results corroborate the propositions of the Self-Determination Theory and the Job Demands-Resources Model. A strong positive relationship between engagement (ENG) and job satisfaction (WS) (0.0769) supports hypothesis H1 proposed in the research. Training, recognition of volunteer contributions, and emotional support are essential elements that enhance ENG among volunteers, leading to higher commitment and satisfaction. This fosters a greater likelihood for volunteers to experience flow, demonstrating autonomy, competence, and positive relationships with their peers (Schaufeli, 2013; Pizarro et al., 2019; Cueto et al., 2024; Ruz et al., 2019).

About H2, the influence of ENG on flow is validated (0.65). Highly dedicated employees who enjoy their tasks and show autonomy, competence, and strong interpersonal relationships tend to lose track of time during their work and are more likely to experience flow (Csikszentmihalyi, 1990).

Hypothesis H3, which establishes the influence of job satisfaction on flow (0.45), is also validated. According to the results, a satisfied volunteer is more likely to perform in a state of flow (Deterding & Cutting, 2023). Job satisfaction is achieved through resource availability, social support, autonomy, and feedback, all promoting the flow state.

For the final model, H4 shows that ENG and WS together explain 70.8% of the flow. This result aligns with the Self-Determination Theory and the Job Demands-Resources Model. Volunteers who are satisfied with their work environment and highly engaged in tasks are likelier to experience flow. Engagement and job satisfaction work synergistically to foster an optimal flow state among volunteers, supporting a holistic approach that considers engagement and job satisfaction as key elements promoting flow (Bellini et al., 2022).

This research holds significant implications for the NGOs studied, aligning with recommendations and principles to provide emotional and professional support to those involved, mainly volunteers. The findings confirm the hypotheses and emphasise the importance of focusing on both variables to promote flow in volunteer-based NGOs, ultimately leading to greater productivity, commitment, and retention within the organisation.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The results confirm that engaged volunteers feel recognised and supported and experience higher job satisfaction (WS). This engagement, characterised by vigour, dedication, and absorption, positively influences the flow state, an optimal experience where individuals are fully immersed in their activity, enjoying it, and feeling in control. WS also plays a significant role in promoting flow, highlighting the need for work environments that provide appropriate challenges, favourable physical conditions, and development opportunities.

The positive relationship between engagement (ENG), job satisfaction (WS), and flow suggests that improving these variables strengthens non-profit organisations' impact and contributes to creating a more inclusive and sustainable work environment. Theories of Self-Determination and Role Theory reinforce that meeting the basic needs for autonomy, competence, and relationships is fundamental for commitment and effectiveness in volunteer work.

Based on these findings, NGOs should implement specific strategies to increase their volunteers' engagement (ENG) and job satisfaction (WS). This includes providing adequate training, regular recognition, and emotional support. Organisations should ensure that the assigned tasks align with volunteers' skills and personal preferences, creating a meaningful and challenging experience that promotes flow. Moreover, improving physical working conditions and offering benefits that enhance perceptions of equity and job security is crucial.

To foster a more inclusive and satisfying work environment, NGOs should involve volunteers in decision-making and offer professional and personal development opportunities. Implementing effective management practices, such as constant feedback and growth opportunities, can significantly increase volunteer satisfaction and engagement, reducing turnover and improving retention.

Finally, future research is suggested to explore additional factors that may influence these dynamics and examine the long-term effects of engagement and job satisfaction on flow.

Limitations

Given that this is a cross-sectional study, a correlation between the variables can only be observed at a specific point in time. This prevents the establishment of definitive causal relationships between engagement, job satisfaction, and the flow state.

The use of standardised instruments may introduce biases. Additionally, the results may not be generalizable to other organisations if they focus on a single non-governmental organisation (NGO).

External factors, such as economic, political, or social changes, also influence the motivation and commitment of volunteers, affecting their flow state. Furthermore, the temporal nature of engagement and job satisfaction evolves, suggesting that a longitudinal study could provide a less biased understanding of these dynamics.

Lastly, not considering other variables that influence the flow state, such as previous volunteer experience or the type of tasks performed, limits the interpretation of the results.

Contributions

NGOs serve as engines of social change for countries seeking to contribute to social development. They rely heavily on the work of their volunteers, making it essential to recognise their efforts. Additionally, it is important to ensure they work in supportive environments where commitment, autonomy, competence, and belonging are core pillars for development and sustainability. Opportunities for training, recognition, and a positive work environment should exist, allowing volunteers to carry out essential tasks with commitment, empowerment, and high motivation.

This study aimed to analyze the influence of engagement (ENG) and job satisfaction (WS) on the flow state of volunteers in a non-governmental organization (NGO). By applying a quantitative methodology, the hypotheses were validated.

Engagement explains more than 65% of the variability in the flow state, highlighting the importance of creating an environment where volunteers feel empowered to contribute to their performance. Recognising their work and offering opportunities to develop their skills and contribute to the organisation are key. Job satisfaction accounts for 45% of the variability in the flow state, underscoring the significance of a healthy work environment where effort is valued and the necessary tools are provided to improve performance. Understanding the flow state in volunteerism is a highly relevant topic requiring further investigation to contribute meaningful insights to the field.

The results emphasise that both engagement and job satisfaction are important factors influencing the flow state of volunteers in NGOs, demonstrating a close relationship between these variables and the flow state. This is crucial for achieving the sustainability of the studied NGO. These organisations need motivated, engaged, and satisfied volunteers to fulfil their mission and play a fundamental role in society. Based on these findings, promoting engagement and job satisfaction represents a central element for NGOs to help achieve a flow state, which increases productivity, commitment, and retention within the organisation.

Acknowledgments

To Cesar Vallejo University for funding the study, which is the result of research from the Doctorate in Administration.

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